

MILITARY SCIENCES

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE MILITARY DECISION-MAKING PROCESS AT THE TACTICAL AND OPERATIONAL LEVEL

*Kerimov E.
colonel*

Military Institute named after Heydar Aliyev, Baku, Azerbaijan

ABSTRACT

The article examines the situation of ensuring the effectiveness of the military decision-making process at the tactical and operational level. The scientific-theoretical and practical aspects of the military decision-making process at the tactical and operational level were studied, intuitive and strategic decision-making and its elements were explained. In the article, the decision-making models in the literature were studied and, according to these models, the application of the military decision-making process at different levels was compared, and a new analysis model was presented to be used in risk, center of gravity and critical factor analyses. It has been estimated that the current military decision-making process needs to be updated to ensure decision-making in this environment, and that it would be appropriate to switch to a natural decision-making model that includes intuitive intelligence rather than normative and descriptive intelligence. The practical importance of the article is to reveal the shortcomings in the decision-making processes of commanders who will have to perform operational tasks at a variable pace in the dynamic and complex environment of the future.

Keywords: military decisions, military decision-making process, natural decision-making, intuitive decision-making, tactical and operational level.

Introduction

The decision-making process in management is the selection of the best among the alternatives for the organization or individual individuals to achieve their goals within the scope of their duties and powers. The most important quality of any manager is his willingness to make important and difficult decisions and the competence to make those decisions. The manager's performance is related to the effectiveness of his decisions. The decision-making process gives the leader the right to make a decision freely by thoroughly analyzing and evaluating the situation. Since the leader makes the decision himself, he is also responsible for its implementation.

A decision environment consists of environments containing certainty, uncertainty, and varying levels of risk. In addition to such environments, time-varying positions, interdisciplinary interactions, complexities, and intangible factors must also be evaluated in the decision-making process. Developments sometimes require decisions to be made in response to sudden situations, and sometimes decisions that require detailed analysis as a result of long-term research.

Based on this, it can be said that higher military educational institutions try to train cadets as both commanders and high-level specialists with a professional personality, intellect, and a modern outlook. Because, in the process of achieving national interests and goals, all officers who start their service in military units and other institutions have to make certain tactical, operational and strategic decisions. This makes it necessary to develop their decision-making and decision-making skills.

Taking into account that decision-making studies are the subject of research in many fields of science, such as political science, sociology, psychology, economics and management, the issues raised in this article

were used from the above-mentioned sciences [1, p. 925-942].

Currently, elements of national power in the field of defense are becoming more and more important. In this context, the effectiveness of national defense depends on the combination of many factors, including military power. The purpose of the mentioned research is to define and limit the combat functions of the military forces, which constitute one of the important pillars of national defense today, and to explain with examples the application of decision and optimization methods to this field. In the field of defense, combat functions at the tactical and operational level are taken into account, other defense elements of national power and applications at the level of joint operations are excluded from the scope [2].

Effective use of armed forces that ensure national security and analysis of military operations in this context, and therefore, military power has become a necessity rather than an option. Future forecasts and research show that defense functions will become increasingly important to countries, and that those who make progress in these areas will have leading roles. International conflicts of interest affect the national and global defense sector as well as all industries and create an important area of competition between international actors. Developed countries base their defense and internal security concepts on the political, economic and cultural control of foreign countries and regions that may pose a threat to them. Technological superiority in the defense industry, particularly in weapons systems, is recognized as having a significant impact on the effectiveness of military operational capabilities. The race to create new weapons systems based on information technology has become indispensable for countries that want to have a say in world security. The defense partnership shows a determination towards the

creation of self-defense systems independent of external sources as today's irreplaceable strategic approaches [3, p. 87-110].

1. The military decision-making process at the natural, tactical and operational levels

Decision making has created important problems for people not only today, but also in the past. Intuitive decision-making techniques based on experience and judgment have been the most widely used methods for finding solutions to decision problems. Methods such as making decisions based on untested truths and errors in the past, following those with experience, or imitating the decisions of other decision makers in similar situations are considered the best examples of these heuristic methods.

But in our modern era, decision-making, especially in the military field, requires a very logical and operational thinking, the right approach. In other words, whether the decision to be made is right or wrong must be understood and analyzed in advance. Otherwise, its effectiveness and efficiency can be quite low.

Therefore, the most important issue in the decision-making process is to ensure that the decision-maker makes the right decision with the help of qualitative and quantitative methods. Whereas in the traditional decision-making process there is a problem of intuition, experience and limited knowledge, in modern approaches a systematic and integrated decision-making process structure comes to the fore. Within the framework of the findings, quantitative decision making techniques help the decision maker to make good decisions.

If we want the decisions we make to be effective, it is important that we follow each of the five stages when making a decision:

- Collection, systematization and analysis of information;
- The issue setting stage;
- Development of alternative options;
- Decision-making stage;
- The stage of implementation of the adopted decisions.

But decision-making is not just about stages. At the same time, apart from these mentioned stages, it is also important to expect three main elements for the process to be effective. These factors are especially important to consider when making a decision:

- Quality of the decision-making process;
- Execution of the given decisions;
- Decision making period.

Since decision-making is apparently a complex process, it needs a wider and comprehensive study. But since we focus on the military decision-making process in this article, we will try to analyze these issues.

Thus, decision-making manifests itself in different forms and levels. An example of them is the military decision-making process at the natural, tactical and operational levels.

Naturalistic decision-making - describes how decisions are made in complex situations and under natural conditions, emphasizing the human factor in the decision-making process. The conditions of the natural

decision-making process are defined as follows: It is not easy to determine the possible courses of action for solving the problem. The situation is uncertain and constantly changing. Because environmental conditions are dynamic, it seems impossible to analyze large network traffic in practice. Natural decision-making is inherently limited in time, high in stress, and limited in information capacity [4].

Naturalistic decision-making studies allow us to understand how people make decisions in real life, in chaotic environments and under difficult conditions, in order to best perform the task assigned to them [5, p. 890-897]. Instead of understanding and explaining mental activities, research on this topic focuses on understanding, planning, mental modeling, designing and using the relevant event [6, p. 78-89].

Natural decision making differs from traditional decision making in four main ways. Of these:

- Features and conditions of the task to be decided;
- Experience level of decision makers;
- Research intention to understand strategies used by individuals;
- It is to understand the areas of interest in the decision-making process [7, p. 111-120].

When these four characteristics are studied, it allows us to determine what the battlefield and operational space should be like.

Military decision-making can also be evaluated at different levels.

- Strategic decisions (allocation of resources, consolidation and modernization of forces)
- Operational decisions (allocation of power and human resources, logistics planning)
- Tactical decisions (target management, tactical operations and optimal deployment planning).

At the operational level, the unit commander creates a picture by imagining the entire process from the beginning to the end of the operation. It curbs this image with operational design. This process constitutes the artistic side of war and differs from the tactical level. While the tactical level is planned with training knowledge and procedural rules, which can also be expressed as theory, the operational level emphasizes the leader's knowledge, foresight, intelligence, and intuition. Available tools, methods and risks are considered to achieve the desired end state.

While at the tactical level, only a limited number of critical factors are analyzed in the name of a systematic approach, at the operational level, this analysis is accompanied by the stages of determining the center of gravity, managing the goal and risks, and determining the final result. If we look at the current situation, both the tactical and operational levels are normative in terms of the decision-making model. But the strategic level is descriptive in nature. Therefore, decision-making models at all levels are based on Newton's concept of rationality, which states that everything is predictable and measurable given the necessary information.

"Officers of the future" - their commanders will have to perform operational tasks at a changing pace in a dynamic and complex environment. For this reason, it is necessary to update the current decision-making

models to ensure that decisions are made in that environment.

The military decision-making process is a model that requires a systematic approach. Predicting the future based on what happened in the past ignores the influence of many factors, especially psychological factors [8, p. 3-20]. A systematic approach examines the whole by breaking it down into parts. Therefore, in this approach, the ontological perception of the object is based on mechanical human nature. It analyzes the parts of the whole as points of connection. When analyzing problems, it focuses on two-way connections and does not care about the connections of the same node with other nodes [9]. Therefore, it is understood that a subject-independent analysis cannot obtain any information about the possible outcomes of the system.

Based on the methodology of "*knowledge follows its object*" as well as "*knowledge follows its method*" existing in all social sciences [10]. It can be concluded that the analyzes carried out in the task analysis stage of the military decision-making process at the tactical and operational level cannot provide a view of the whole picture. The social systems of the real world are built with collective behaviors and electronic networks, along with command-management relations, and it is estimated that in the near future, different communicative action models such as robotics and artificial intelligence will come into play [11]. For this reason, it is necessary to digitize the factors related to the factors and use the statistical cluster analysis technique, or optimize the use of programs that provide qualitative data analysis.

A good decision requires, first of all, the right information, at the right time and in the right format. Formats (existing traditions) are good for decision-making, but commanders should not be bound by formats, but should be able to be creative and have the ability to think independently. As a result of the analysis of the task, the main idea to be expressed by the commander should be based on a detailed analysis of all factors [12].

It should not be forgotten that the human mind is inadequate to analyze the increasingly complex information. To get a holistic perspective, systems capable of comprehensive analysis are needed, especially artificial intelligence and quantum computers. By artificial intelligence, we mean a single system of interdependency modeling, cognitive connections, language-related inputs and outputs, video and image interpretation, problem solving, and prediction. In addition, since the operational level is linked to the strategic level, there is a need for officers with greater knowledge of national power elements. Making operational decisions in increasingly complex combat conditions will only be possible through natural decision-making.

2. Intuitive decision making

The operative level, which constitutes the artistic direction of the fight, should include intuitive elements as well as scientific methodology (it should be based on intuition). Intuition is not the opposite of rationality or a process of random guesswork. Intuition is a sophisticated way of thinking used by professionals who have honed their skills through years of experience in a field.

That is, it can be understood that since the lessons learned through experience are logical and valid, the same applies to intuition.

The Chinese general and military strategist **Sun Tzu** explored the essential role of an ideal commander and suggested that such a leader should rely on his experience and intuition to make creative and free decisions [13].

The French strategic theorist **Jomini**, using similar expressions to Sun Tzu, noted that: "*If the skill of the general is one of the most reliable elements of victory, it will be clear that the fair selection of generals is one of the most sensitive topics of state science and an important component of the country's military policy*" [14, p. 67].

Emphasizing the importance of making quick decisions in order to take advantage of important opportunities, Sun Tzu indicated that a leader should believe in the right moments by stating that: "*A general who does not understand his own abilities, or who does not understand the art of agility and expediency when an opportunity arises to attack the enemy, is left and right in great confusion. Looking, he will proceed hesitantly and will not be able to make any plans*" [15, p. 87-88].

Clausewitz, the German commander, Prussian general and military theorist, the author of the famous treatise "**On War**", stated that not only reason and intelligence are enough, but that military service has scientific foundations as well as art. He also stated that the undeniable importance of intuition and judgment is a fact: "*it is an intuition of a kind of truth that is solid, a kind of truth that cannot be based on anything*" [15, p. 102]. In other words, a person who is always active should rely on his intuition, which sometimes arises from his intelligence, develops with thinking, and often shows the right path.

Mental activity is separated from logical and mathematical calculations of basic sciences. Mental activity then becomes an art in the broadest sense of the word, in which the power of decision is based on a more or less intuitive comparison of all factors and accompanying circumstances.

Assumptions that systematic and analytical options are better than intuitive options in management have disappeared with studies investigating intuitiveness in decision-making [16, p. 246-275]. "**Routine decisions**" of concern to tactical-level managers are the technical work of deciding how to manage resources efficiently according to established procedures. Irregular decisions of interest to strategic and operational level managers are more complex and multi-component, requiring more situational awareness and adaptation, identifying the problem, proposing creative solutions, and assessing what will happen. The importance of decisions to be made at this level requires leaders to have strong intuition as well as analytical thinking skills.

A decision-making process is a habit or form of behavior that a leader acquires/learns. Both external and internal factors play a role here. The decision-making model used by a leader represents a process that occurs over time. In this process, the decision-making ex-

periences of the decision-maker are feedback loops resulting from his constant interaction with the environment. In particular, these feedback loops, which play an important role in the *development of people's individual characteristics, are extremely vital for the identification of leadership candidates and their career development.*

In the new training model that will be created, a system should be created that allows leaders to practice on as many different scenarios as possible in terms of content in order to make decision-making processes a habit. On the other hand, in order to avoid the monotony caused by sticking to stereotypes, it is necessary to introduce intermediate situations to leaders, to ensure the change of internal and external factors, and ultimately to allow them to find the most correct and optimal solution within themselves. In addition, different perspectives can be gained by using short but multiple scenarios covering different areas rather than using a single long-term scenario in this training.

3. Strategy and its elements

Although wars are described as tactical, operational, and strategic, these three levels actually evolve into a political effect that is built upon each other in the form of a pyramid. According to Clausewitz, *"war is just a continuation of politics by other means"* [15, p. 45] this process, which finds its essence in the short and concise form of the sentence, actually covers all three levels of military strategy. According to the British military theorist and military historian **Liddell Hart**, *"the art of deploying and using military power to achieve political goals"* [17, p. 447] strategy is concerned not only with the movement of forces, but also with their effects. To create this effect, all three combat levels must be considered and evaluated together. He says about this: *"Although strategy and tactics are always a convenient topic for discussion, they can never be divided into separate parts. Because they not only affect each other, but also merge with each other"* [17, p. 447].

The opinions of other specialists Kane and Lonsdale on the same topic are also quite important: *"The relationship between tactical activities and strategy is interesting for the operational level, which can think conceptually and physically"* [18, p. 37].

From this idea, we conclude that to avoid any inconsistency between such a tightly integrated structure, it is of great importance to correctly draw and define the path between military power and political goal, i.e., strategy. In other words, the political objective must be clear and understandable at all levels of command. A clear understanding of how military forces can best serve this purpose is needed, and an achievable military objective must be defined.

The success of the strategy depends, first of all, on the correct calculation and coordination of goals and means. The creation and acquisition of armed forces is an obvious means, and their use is the goal [15, p. 56].

Gray, who prepared the most comprehensive work on the multidimensional nature of strategy, defines strategy in three categories and 17 dimensions [19, p. 25]. According to his thinking, although all wars

have the same character, in fact, each war manifests itself differently in its details: *"Besides its basic character (regular or irregular), every war is affected by a number of other factors. These include the geography of the battlefield, the strategic culture of the parties to the conflict, and the available technology"* [18, p. 37].

Thus, summarizing the opinions of the experts mentioned above, it can be concluded that Clausewitz mentions the elements of strategy as spiritual, physical, mathematical, geographical and statistical elements, which coincides with what Gray refers to as usable technology. What Gray conceptualizes as strategic culture is a meaningful and complex expression of what Clausewitz describes as moral values and military intuition.

Strategy is as much about human relations as it is about politics. In this field we need from the higher powers of the mind the power of synthesis, the power of judgment and decision-making, these powers must rise to such a level of spiritual vision that it can quickly grasp and eliminate thousands of vague ideas. Thus, although the geography of the battlefield and the available technology are considered without exception at all three levels of combat, the issues related to the strategic culture mentioned by Clausewitz stand out as the most important issue.

Conclusion

From our analysis and research, we once again come to the conclusion that war as a whole is an activity that combines scientific and artistic elements. For this reason, it does not seem possible to reduce the process used in the planning of the activities to be carried out to precise rules, as in positive sciences. It can be concluded that it is considered more appropriate to use what the leaders have acquired from their past experiences and knowledge filtered through the rational mind. This is considered more correct from a strategic point of view.

The impatience of a commander who knows the theories of war very well, but cannot evaluate the situation, cannot put his intuition in his mind, and on the other hand, is cold-blooded and impractical due to his characteristics, is understandable. Also, the commander, who is the instigator and provider of the material and moral factors that the army needs, must use both his mind and emotions to provide this.

Although the military decision-making process developed within the logic of analytical thinking is sufficient at lower levels because it requires less imagination, some difficulties arise when moving from tactical to strategic thinking. Here, first of all, the analyzes in the process should be reconstructed from a holistic perspective, all kinds of technological possibilities should be used, and artificial intelligence should be activated. Second, a new educational model should be developed that will increase the effectiveness of intuitive decision-making, which is seen as necessary when analyzed from a cultural point of view, to activate the emotions and thoughts of the person who will make the final decision. During the implementation of the mentioned model, it is considered appropriate to provide future commanders with various regions and intermediate sit-

uations within a large number of scenarios and to increase the imagination of the battlefield. Exposed to different scenarios in an environment supported by visual elements, commanders will have the opportunity to identify and use the intellectual dimensions of their multiple intelligences as well as the emotional and intuitive dimensions.

Decision-making activities are closely related to combat levels, and decisions made at the strategic, operational, and tactical levels are critical to achieving the desired end state at the political level. In this sense, by writing those decisions correctly, it should be assessed that the strategy and strategic culture that defines it is important for the country and the organization, and that it is influenced by culture.

As a result of the analysis, we come to the conclusion that the cultural level and strategic capabilities of the country and the organization should be taken into account in determining the military strategy. The correct promotion of the strategy can undoubtedly influence the operational-tactical level and create conditions for ensuring the correct and timely use of military forces. Therefore, when analyzed from a cultural point of view, it is thought that the development of the commander's intuition and judgment in the planning and execution process is extremely important and will bring success at the tactical and operational level.

References

1. Julie, G. Naturalistic decision making and organizations: reviewing pragmatic science / A.Banks, L.Millward, O.Kyriakidou // *Organization studies*, - 2006. - vol. 27(7), - p. 925-942.
2. Okan, Y. Davranışsal karar verme düşünme problem çözme / Y. Okan - Ankara: Detay yayıncılık, - 2016, - 94 s.
3. Aplak, H. Karar verme yöntemleri ve askeri muharebe fonksiyonları alanlarına yönelik uygulamaları // *Güvenlik bilimleri dergisi*, - mayıs 2018. cilt 7, sayı 1, s. 87-110. <https://doi.org/10.28956/gbd.422799>
4. Bryant, D.J. Making naturalistic decision making “fast and frugal”: [Elektronik resource]/ URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228937089_Making_naturalistic_decision_making_fast_and_frugal - 2002.
5. Helsloot, I., Groenendaal, J. Naturalistic decision making in forensic science: toward a better understanding of decision making by forensic team leaders // *Journal of forensic sciences*, - 2011. 56(4), - p. 890-897.
6. Poliç, M. Decision making: Between rationality and reality // - Croatia: *Journal of interdisciplinary description of complex systems*, - 2009. 7(2), - p. 78-89.
7. Zsombok, C. E. Naturalistic decision making research and improving team decision making / In C. E. Zsombok & G. Klein (Eds.) // *Naturalistic decision making*, - 1997. Vol. 50, Iss. 3, - p. 111-120, <https://doi.org/10.1518/001872008X288385>
8. Dudi (Yehuda), A. Process of military decision making // *Military and strategic affairs*, - 2013. Vol. 5, Iss. 2 (September), - p. 3-20
9. Pehlivan, O. Aile tanımı ve ilişkilerinin toplumsal olarak inşası. Doktora tezi / O. Pehlivan. - Ankara: Hacettepe Üniversitesi, 2017. - 259 s.
10. Sayer, A. Method in social science: a realist approach. Second edition / A. Sayer. - London: Routledge, - 2006. - 336 p. ISBN: 978-0415076074
11. Sapaty, P.S. Holistic analysis and management of distributed social systems / P.S. Sapaty, - Springer, -2019. - 341 p. ISBN: 978-3-030-13197-5
12. Vego, M. The The Bureaucratization of the U.S. Military decisionmaking process // -Washington: National Defense University Press, - Jan. 9, 2018.
13. Handel, M.I. Savaşın ustaları. Klasik stratejiler / M.I.Handel. - İstanbul: Doruk yayınları, - 2004, - 592 s. ISBN: 9789755534282
14. Jomini, A.H. Savaş sanatının ana hatları / A.H.Jomini. - İstanbul: Doruk yayınları, - 2002. - 164 s. ISBN: 9789756557273
15. Sun, Tzu. The art of war / çev. Samuel B. Griffith / New York: Oxford University Press, -1971, - 224 p. ISBN: 978-0195015409
15. Clausewitz, C.V. Savaş üzerine / C.V.Clausewitz. - İstanbul: Alfa Yayınları, - 2018, - 830 s. ISBN: 9789755534725
16. Mintzberg, H., Raisinghani, D. and Theoret, A. The structure of “unstructured” decision processes // *Administrative Science Quarterly*, - 1976. 21, - p. 246-275. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2392045>
17. Liddell Hart, B.H. Strateji dolaylı tutum / B.H. Liddell Hart. - İstanbul: Doruk Yayınları, -2022. - 584 s. ISBN: 9789755539164
18. Kane, T.M. ve Lonsdale, D.J. Çağdaş stratejiyi anlamak / T.M.Kane, ve D.J. Lonsdale, - İstanbul: Doruk yayınları, - 2016. - 512 s.
19. Gray, C.S. Modern strategy / C.S.Gray. - Oxford: Oxford University Press, - 1999. - 432 p. ISBN: 9780198782513